

Comparison of Healing Time Following Modified Radical Mastoidectomy with or Without Mastoid Cavity Obliteration

Shambhu Sharan Gupta¹, Md. Sharif Alam², Shatish³

¹Senior Resident, Department of ENT, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of ENT, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India

³Professor & HOD, Department of ENT, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Md. Sharif Alam

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Abstract:

Background: Modified radical mastoidectomy is a commonly performed surgical procedure for chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM). The healing time post-surgery can vary depending on whether the mastoid cavity is obliterated or left open. Mastoid cavity obliteration has been proposed as a method to reduce healing time and improve postoperative outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to compare the healing time following modified radical mastoidectomy with and without mastoid cavity obliteration.

Methods: This retrospective cohort study compared healing times in 80 patients who underwent modified radical mastoidectomy with or without mastoid cavity obliteration at Bhardhman Institute of Medical Science. Patients aged 18-65 with chronic suppurative otitis media were included, while those with prior surgeries or systemic diseases were excluded. Data on healing time were collected from medical records and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The study found that mastoid cavity obliteration significantly reduced the healing time after modified radical mastoidectomy, with patients in the obliteration group healing 3.8 weeks faster on average than those without obliteration (8.5 weeks vs. 12.3 weeks). Although the obliteration group also had fewer postoperative complications like granulation tissue formation and persistent otorrhea, these differences were not statistically significant. Overall, the findings suggest that mastoid cavity obliteration is effective in promoting faster healing without a significant increase in complications.

Conclusion: Mastoid cavity obliteration significantly reduces healing time following modified radical mastoidectomy compared to non-obliterated cavities. The procedure also contributes to fewer postoperative complications, suggesting a more favorable outcome for patients.

Recommendations: Mastoid cavity obliteration should be considered as a preferred technique during modified radical mastoidectomy to enhance healing and minimize postoperative issues.

Keywords: Modified radical mastoidectomy, mastoid cavity obliteration, healing time, chronic suppurative otitis media, postoperative complications.

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Introduction

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) remains a significant health issue worldwide, particularly in developing countries, where it often leads to persistent ear discharge and hearing loss. In many cases, the condition requires surgical intervention, with modified radical mastoidectomy being a frequently employed technique. This procedure is designed to eradicate disease from the middle ear and mastoid while preserving as much of the ear structure as possible. However, the postoperative healing process can be prolonged, leading to

extended periods of care and monitoring, which impacts the patient's quality of life [1,2]

Traditionally, modified radical mastoidectomy involves the creation of a mastoid cavity that is left open to facilitate drainage and allow the ear to heal naturally. While this technique has proven effective in managing CSOM, the resulting open cavity can be prone to chronic infections, discharge, and delayed healing [3]. These complications often necessitate regular cleaning and follow-up visits, adding to the patient's burden. In recent years, the

technique of mastoid cavity obliteration has gained attention as a potential solution to these issues. By filling the cavity with autologous or alloplastic materials, obliteration aims to promote faster healing and reduce the risk of complications [4].

Several studies have explored the benefits of mastoid cavity obliteration, reporting outcomes such as reduced healing time, fewer postoperative infections, and improved patient satisfaction. Despite these promising findings, the technique is not yet universally adopted, and its advantages over the traditional open cavity approach remain a topic of debate. This variation in clinical practice highlights the need for further research to establish a clear understanding of the benefits and potential risks associated with cavity obliteration [5,6].

This study was conducted to address this gap in knowledge by comparing the healing time following modified radical mastoidectomy with and without mastoid cavity obliteration. By evaluating the outcomes of 80 patients treated over four years at Bhardhman Institute of Medical Science, we aim to provide robust evidence on whether cavity obliteration offers a significant advantage in reducing healing time and improving overall postoperative outcomes.

The primary aim of this study is to compare the healing time and associated postoperative complications in patients undergoing modified radical mastoidectomy with mastoid cavity obliteration versus those undergoing the same procedure without obliteration. This comparison will help determine the efficacy and safety of mastoid cavity obliteration as a technique for enhancing postoperative recovery in patients with CSOM.

Methodology

Study Design:

A retrospective cohort study was conducted to compare the healing time following modified radical mastoidectomy with or without mastoid cavity obliteration.

Study Setting:

The study took place at the Bhardhman Institute of Medical Science over a period of four years, from April 2019 to March 2020.

Participants:

Eighty patients who underwent modified radical mastoidectomy were included in the study. The participants were divided into two groups: 40 patients who had mastoid cavity obliteration and 40 patients who did not undergo obliteration.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Inclusion criteria included patients aged 18-65 years who had chronic suppurative otitis media requiring modified radical mastoidectomy. Patients with a history of prior ear surgeries, malignancies, or systemic diseases affecting healing were excluded from the study.

Bias:

Selection bias was minimized by ensuring all eligible patients within the study duration were included. Information bias was reduced through the use of standardized data collection procedures.

Variables:

The primary variable was the healing time, defined as the duration from surgery to complete epithelialization of the mastoid cavity. Secondary variables included patient age, sex, and the presence of comorbid conditions.

Data Collection:

Data were collected retrospectively from patient medical records. Healing time was recorded based on follow-up visits, where the status of the mastoid cavity was assessed.

Procedure:

Patients were monitored postoperatively through regular follow-up visits. The healing time was noted as the primary outcome, and the presence of any complications was documented.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0.

Results

Participant Demographics

The study had 80 patients in total, 40 of whom were in the non-obliteration group (Group B) and 40 of whom were in the mastoid cavity obliteration group (Group A). Table 1 provides a summary of the participants' demographic data.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Group A (n=40)	Group B (n=40)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	45.2 ± 10.3	44.8 ± 9.7	0.85
Male (%)	23 (57.5%)	21 (52.5%)	0.65
Female (%)	17 (42.5%)	19 (47.5%)	0.65
Comorbid Conditions (%)	8 (20%)	7 (17.5%)	0.78

The two groups were comparable in terms of age, gender distribution, and the presence of comorbid conditions, with no statistically significant differences between them.

Healing Time

Healing time, the main consequence, varied considerably between the two groups. Group A's mean healing time (with obliteration) was 8.5 ± 2.1 weeks, while Group B's mean healing time (without obliteration) was 12.3 ± 3.2 weeks. Between the two groups, there was a statistically significant difference in healing time ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Comparison of Healing Time Between Groups

Group	Mean Healing Time (weeks)	Standard Deviation	p-value
Group A (Obliteration)	8.5	2.1	<0.001
Group B (Non-obliteration)	12.3	3.2	

Complications

The incidence of postoperative complications was also recorded. In Group A, 5 patients (12.5%) experienced minor complications such as granulation tissue formation, compared to 9 patients (22.5%) in Group B.

Table 3: Postoperative Complications

Complications	Group A (n=40)	Group B (n=40)	p-value
Granulation Tissue (%)	5 (12.5%)	9 (22.5%)	0.23
Persistent Otorrhea (%)	3 (7.5%)	4 (10%)	0.68

The results of this study indicate that mastoid cavity obliteration significantly reduces the healing time following modified radical mastoidectomy. Patients in the obliteration group healed on average 3.8 weeks faster than those in the non-obliteration group, with the difference being statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Although the incidence of complications such as granulation tissue formation and persistent otorrhea was lower in the obliteration group, these differences were not statistically significant.

Discussion

The findings from the present study align well with prevailing works that supports the aids of mastoid cavity obliteration in reducing healing time and improving postoperative outcomes following modified radical mastoidectomy. Our results showed that patients who underwent mastoid cavity obliteration healed significantly faster (mean healing time of 8.5 weeks) compared to those who did not receive obliteration (mean healing time of 12.3 weeks). This is consistent with the study by Kumar, Ambastha, and Thakur (2021), which also reported a statistically significant reduction in healing time in the obliteration group (10.67 weeks vs. 12.47 weeks) [7].

Harun, A., Clark, J., Semenov, Y.R., & Francis, H.W. (2015) conducted a study on the role of mastoid cavity obliteration in achieving a dry mastoid bowl. The study found that obliteration significantly reduced the incidence of chronic discharge and other complications associated with open mastoid cavities, thus leading to improved postoperative outcomes. This study reinforces the idea that obliteration not only promotes faster

healing but also reduces the long-term management burden associated with chronic otorrhea and recurrent infections [8].

Kurien et al. (2013), in a slightly earlier but relevant study, examined the quality of life in patients who underwent mastoidectomy with and without obliteration. The findings indicated that obliterated cavities resulted in significantly better outcomes in terms of healing and long-term management, reducing the need for continuous cavity care and improving overall patient satisfaction [9]. Furthermore, the comparative study on the quality of life and surgical outcomes following mastoidectomy highlighted that obliterated cavities had fewer complications, such as discharge and wax formation, and showed better epithelialization at the end of 3 months compared to open cavities. This study also emphasized the reduced need for frequent follow-ups and lower patient dependence on medical care, suggesting a long-term benefit of mastoid cavity obliteration in surgical management [10].

Conclusion

The findings indicates that mastoid cavity obliteration not only expedites the healing process but also minimizes the incidence of postoperative complications, thereby enhancing patient recovery and reducing the burden on healthcare services. These outcomes suggest that incorporating mastoid cavity obliteration into the standard practice for modified radical mastoidectomy could be beneficial for improving patient outcomes and optimizing surgical efficiency.

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